

Improving Mental Health Literacy among Young Adults: A Pretest Post-test Study

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Mental health is one of the most important determinants of our health and well-being. It is a state of mind in which we recognise our abilities, strengths and weaknesses and use them wisely to deal with various life stressors and lead a productive and functional life, contributing to self as well as the community. Mental health literacy (MHLs) enables us to create knowledge and understanding of mental health and well-being practices, and also about recognising and addressing mental distress and mental ill-health. The aim of this study is to find out the level of mental health literacy among college students. For the same reason, a total of 22 students from different disciplines were selected for the study. A pre-test post-test experimental design was used for the study. 't' test was computed to analyze the data collected using Mental Health Literacy Questionnaire (Raghavan et al., 2023). The result shows there is no significant difference between pre-test and post-test scores on Mental Health Literacy. However, when comparing the mean score, the post-test showed a higher mean score than pre-test, suggesting that the training may have had a positive influence on mental health literacy. Therefore, it can be inferred that long-term training will have a significant impact on the mental health literacy of young adults.

Keywords: Mental health literacy, well being, stress, anxiety and relaxation

Nowadays, poor mental health is a global concern. One in four are affected by some of the mental health issues worldwide (World Health Organization, 2013). This issue is particularly significant in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) like India, where mental health often receives limited funding and attention. While individuals may experience various challenges related to poor mental health (Raghavan et al., 2023). Mental health literacy (MHL) has attracted considerable worldwide attention, especially following the launch of the World Health Organization's (WHO) Mental Health Action Plan (2013-2030). This initiative highlights the crucial role of mental health in achieving universal health coverage. Here comes the importance of mental health literacy programs (Kookal et al., 2025).

'Mental Health Literacy' (MHL), the term was initially introduced by Jorm et al. (1997) who defined it as 'knowledge and beliefs about mental health conditions which aid their recognition, management or prevention' (Raghavan et al., 2022). Reducing the stigma associated with mental illness and educating people about all the different services are the primary objectives of mental health literacy. The ability to identify specific illnesses or types of psychological distress, knowledge and beliefs about associated risks, causes, and self-help interventions, awareness and ideas about professional help that is available, attitudes that support recognition and appropriate

help-seeking, and how to seek mental health support are some of the components that make up mental health literacy (Sampaio, Gonclaves, & Sequerra, 2022).

There are mainly two types of social stigma: 1) Societal stigma refers to the disapproval or discrimination directed toward an individual because of visible social traits that set them apart from the rest of society. 2) Self-stigma refers to 'persons with mental illness, living in a culture steeped in stigmatizing images, may accept these notions and suffer diminished self-esteem and self-efficacy (Raghavan et al., 2022). This study mainly explores the mental health literacy of college students in Kerala.

Mental Health Literacy of College Students

Young adults bring significant life changes during their college days. At this stage, students must develop independence, manage academic demands, and adjust to unfamiliar social and economic environments. As a result, many experiences heightened levels of stress, anxiety, and other mental health issues. Individuals aged 15-29 are especially vulnerable to developing mental health disorders (Elkin, 2025). Mental health literacy (MHL) is one's knowledge, skills, and attitude to identify, assess, and manage mental health issues, which is important for psychological well-being. It helps people notice signs, reduce stigma, and ask for help when necessary (Jorm et al., 1997). This literacy will help them to understand their mental health condition, seek support on time and different types of support systems available in Kerala. In Kerala, the beliefs, attitudes, and cultural frameworks that shape mental health and experiences of mental illness of people.

This study is an attempt to explore the knowledge of young adults regarding mental health, mental disorders, their causes and symptoms, and the treatment services available. In many educational systems, mental health receives very little importance. In the context of India, psychology or mental health is not included in the regular curriculum. As a result, even among the educated population, there is often a lack of awareness about mental disorders

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and the availability of treatment options. Mental health literacy is an important factor in building a healthy and high-quality community or society. A low level of mental health literacy prevents individuals from recognizing signs of distress in themselves or others, which can hinder timely help-seeking and access to support (Raghavan et al., 2022). Enhancing mental health literacy is essential for promoting appropriate help-seeking behaviors and improving access to support across urban, rural, and tribal communities. A general lack of awareness about mental health within the public can contribute to stigma and discrimination toward individuals living with mental illness (Cadigan, Lee, & Larimer, 2019).

College students are considered the backbone of every nation; therefore, this study seeks to explore the level of mental health literacy among young adults. Mental health literacy plays a vital role in fostering respect for people experiencing psychological distress, encouraging self-care, promoting supportive care for others, and reducing stigma (Mboweni, Mphasha, & Skaal, 2024). For individuals with mental health challenges and their family caregivers, improved mental health literacy can significantly enhance their ability to understand and manage mental health conditions effectively.

Objective of the Study

To assess the level of mental health literacy among college students.

Hypothesis of the Study

There will be a significant difference between pre-test and post-test scores on Mental Health Literacy.

Method

Participants

The sample consisted of 25 female college students selected using a random sampling technique from 11 different disciplines, including Arts, Science, and Management. Prior to participation, informed consent was obtained from all students, and only those who provided consent were included in the study. All participants were female, and their ages ranged from 18 to 21 years.

Research Design

A pre-test and post-test experimental design was employed to assess the effectiveness of a mental health literacy intervention among

college students.

Measure

Mental Health Literacy Questionnaire (MHLQ) developed by Raghavan et al. (2023) was used to assess the level of mental health literacy among the participants. The questionnaire contains a total of 35 items. This is actually an adaptation of MHLq-SVa, there for retain the psychometric properties of its original version. The reliability of the questionnaire was 0.81.

Procedure

The study was conducted in three phases:

Pre-test Phase: During the pre-test phase, the mental health literacy levels of the participants were assessed using the Mental Health Literacy Questionnaire (MHLQ). The questionnaire was administered to the selected students, and their responses were recorded.

Training Phase: The training phase lasted for six months. Various programs were organized by the investigators to enhance awareness of mental health literacy (MHL). These included awareness classes conducted by mental health experts, stress management training sessions incorporating relaxation techniques and mindfulness practices, and an exhibition aimed at promoting mental health literacy.

Post-test Phase: After the completion of all awareness and training programs, the participants were re-administered the MHLQ. Their responses were recorded to assess changes in mental health literacy levels.

Statistical Analysis

The recorded Pre-test and Post- test scores are analysed using paired sample “t” test.

Results and Discussion

Preliminary Analysis

Prior to conducting inferential analyses, the assumptions of normality were assessed using descriptive statistics, histogram inspection, and the Shapiro-Wilk test. Data were collected from 25 female college students enrolled at a prominent institution in Southern Kerala, India. Table (1) summarizes the descriptive statistics and Shapiro-Wilk test results for the pre-test, post-test, and difference scores (Post-Pre) for Mental Health Literacy.

Table 1

Descriptive Statistics and Normality Test Results for Mental Health Literacy (N = 22)

Variable	Mean	Median	SD	Skewness	Kurtosis	Shapiro-Wilk-W	p
Pre-test score	112.45	112.50	9.34	-.253	-.954	.961	.507
Post-test Score	115.32	117	8.38	-.682	.338	.962	.528
Difference (Post-Pre)	2.86	3.50	11.07	-.595	.598	.951	.335

As shown in Table 1, the pre-test scores had a mean of 112.45 (*SD* = 9.34) and a median of 112.50. The post-test scores had a mean of 115.32 (*SD* = 8.38) and a median of 117, while the difference scores had a mean of 2.86 (*SD* = 11.07) and a median of 3.50. The similarity among the mean, median, and mode for all variables supports the assumption of normality.

Skewness values for pre-test, post-test score and difference scores

are -.253, -.682 and -.595, respectively. Skewness and kurtosis scores indicate approximately symmetric and mesokurtic distributions. The Shapiro-Wilk test results (pre-test: *W* = 0.961, *p* = 0.507; post-test: *W* = 0.962, *p* = 0.528; difference: *W* = 0.951, *p* = 0.335) all exceeded the 0.05 threshold, confirming that the data did not significantly deviate from normality. Visual inspection of histograms (Figures 1-3) showed roughly bell-shaped distributions for all three scores, further supporting the normality assumption.

Overall, the results indicate that Mental Health Literacy scores, under both pre-test and post-test conditions, were approximately normally distributed among the sample, satisfying the assumptions for parametric inferential analyses.

Figure 1

Pre-test Scores for Mental Health Literacy

Figure 2

Post-test Score for Mental Health Literacy

Table 2

Paired t-test for Pre-test and Post-test Scores on Mental Health Literacy (N = 22)

Variable	Pre-test Mean	Score SD	Post-test Mean	Score SD	t
Mental Health Literacy	112.45	9.34	115.32	8.38	1.21

Based on these results obtained, hypothesis (1), which states that “There will be a significant difference between pre-test and post-test scores on Mental Health Literacy,” is rejected.

The study results indicate there is no significant difference in the mental health literacy among the pre-test and post-test analysis. This may be due to the short duration and limited number activities in the intervention programs. Although the post-test mean score is slightly

Figure 3

Difference Scores (Post-Pre) for Mental Health Literacy

Comparison between Pre-test and Post-test Scores on Mental Health Literacy

To test Hypothesis 1, which stated that “There will be a significant difference between pre-test and post-test scores on Mental Health Literacy,” a paired-sample t-test was conducted. The analysis compared scores before and after the awareness session on mental health literacy among 25 college students. Details of the analysis computed are presented in Table 2.

The outcomes from the post-test ($M = 115.32, SD = 8.38$) were moderately higher than the pre-test results ($M = 112.45, SD = 9.34$), as shown in Table 2, revealing that there may have been a little increase in college students' awareness of knowledge regarding mental health as a result of the intervention. At the 0.05 level, the paired t-test's t-value of 1.21, however, was not statistically significant. This suggests that there is no statistically significant increase in the sample's mental health literacy following the awareness workshop. The results obtained reveal that to have a meaningful effect on students' mental health literacy, extended or frequent sessions must be provided. Numerous studies in this field also highlight the fact that meaningful changes among college students frequently require longer or more frequent interventions. Lai, Lien, Chen, and Lin (2022) state that the MHL curriculum may increase the level of MHL among undergraduate students. This highlights the importance of including mental health literacy as a teaching subject in all disciplines along with frequent proper awareness programs in college and university levels.

higher than of pre-test, this findings underscores the importance of mental health awareness program among youth.

Kerala State Mental Health Authority and National Health Mission report that Keralites across to different age groups suffer from various mental health conditions. For instance, 9% of the population suffering from Depression, besides depression bipolar, and alcohol related mental disorders also prevalent among the

population (Shaji, 2017). Kim et al. (2023) founded that MHL components, knowledge of mental illnesses and treatments and awareness of campus mental health resources were positively associated with help-seeking, while the ability to recognize mental distress in others was negatively associated. These findings suggest that targeted education on campus services and personal mental health knowledge may enhance help-seeking behavior among youth. This is an attempt to assess the level of mental health literacy among college students. Once we aware about the literacy level we can design appropriate interventions based on the need of the target population. This is high time to address the mental health concerns and implement programs aimed to enhancing Mental Health Literacy.

Conclusion

The aim of this study is to assess the level of mental health literacy among college going students. As we know the mental health of young age is a growing concern today. This study is actually a try to assess the extent to which the young adults possessing Mental Health Literacy. Although Kerala was a state of highest literacy, the prevalence of mental health issues is very common; this highlights the critical importance of promoting mental health literacy alongside general literacy. Such study will help to identify the need for mental health literacy awareness programs and further researches to improve the quality of life of individuals. The finding of the study also supports the same. Therefore sustained long-term awareness programs are necessary to enhance the Mental Health literacy of youth. The study also implies the need for policymakers and educational authorities to strengthen accessible, youth-friendly mental health services within colleges and local communities to ensure timely support and better mental health outcomes.

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